

YES, AI WILL REPLACE YOUR PROCUREMENT JOB.

By Nolan Menachemson

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The question isn't whether AI will replace or augment our Procurement jobs. That is an old question.

Technology is more advanced than most people think. In medicine, in engineering, in office jobs, we have existing capabilities to do things that most people do not believe is currently possible.

However, as I write this, a raft of government and corporate Procurement teams, globally, are hiring consultants to rewrite their suite of Procurement templates so Procurement Officers can continue to populate new Procurement templates manually, full of human error, and at the speed of a snail.

There are three reasons why cutting-edge technology is not widely used commercially:

1. The first reason is that outside of Proofs of Concept, organisations typically do not enter into contracts with suppliers for solutions not yet packaged for public consumption. Corporations prefer to buy goods and services solutions with established service levels and benchmark-able pricing.

2. The second reason why cutting-edge technology is not widely available is policy. If the risks of a new tech are unknown, it is challenging to build rules around its safe, effective use.

3. A third reason is technology arrives suddenly and disruptively, rather than unfolding slowly at a pace many people can emotionally handle. At first, the corporate governance teams create a mountain of rules to stop staff using it. Here are some recent examples:

- women being allowed to vote.
- credit cards.
- USB devices.
- open-source software.
- mobile phones for work.
- cloud with data stored offshore.
- ride-share. - work from home.
- autonomous vehicles.

- ChatGPT.

For these three reasons, many if not most corporate (including. gov) organisations have either prohibited or restricted the use of ChatGPT at work.

For the last two years, we've heard from industry that generative AI will not replace our jobs but rather augment (assist) us in the performance of these duties. It sounds a bit like "be alert but not alarmed". In the 1950s, government instructed schools to put children under their desks during a nuclear attack.

The advice on AI sounds soothing, but it is advice relevant only to the baby years of this powerful technology. The question of Replace vs Augment is a Baby Years question.

The AI baby years end in 2025.

Once the baby becomes a toddler and starts walking, the question will evolve. AI is fundamentally not designed to duplicate human work. Machines work differently. They won't follow our processes. At least not in the way we think about these sacrosanct processes. The "I" stands for intelligence.

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In 2025, AI will start to evolve from a cute but powerful ChatGPT textbox into more commercially packaged solutions. One of those types of solutions will be Procurement software robots that can work within Procurement policy rules to identify sourcing strategies (e.g., open market tender) and develop the multiple document paperwork in seconds - based on the OEM's (original equipment manufacturer) deep learning from its other Customers.

What currently takes two staff three months to write will be available in minutes:

- Approval docs.
- Evaluation Plans.
- Tenders.
- Evaluation Reports.
- Evaluation scoring (analysing supplier responses).
- Supplier notifications by email.
- Lawyer-quality Contracts.

It's coming. If it isn't coming, then software companies like OpenAI and Google, that have invested billions of dollars in deep learning and generative AI applications, will have upgraded the World's best search engines, instead of creating autonomous intelligence.

The horse did not evolve to walk alongside humans. Modern medicine is not designed to work alongside shamans.

Factory robots don't mix shifts with human workers. Airlines don't offer steamboat travel as an alternative to flying. Humans are present, and with critical responsibilities, but don't confuse their jobs: they don't do the same work as machines. Humans, that once performed these jobs, evolved into different jobs. It happens in a step-by-step process:

1. Humans pull a plough.
2. Humans use an ox to pull a plough.
3. Humans invent a machine to plough, and humans manually control the machine.
4. The machine drives itself, with humans onboard for safety and compliance reasons.
5. Humans eventually lose interest in sitting onboard as the number of safety-related incidents fall below 0.1%.

AI won't augment humans, no matter how much politicians want us to soothe us to believe. Sure, humans will need to be present, but in different roles with a curatorial focus. And even those curatorial roles will evolve.

The day is fast approaching where the traditional Procurement Officer role will be replaced by software. Most Procurement people will evolve into new jobs. The smart ones will see the writing on the wall now and position their learning in preparation to evolve into sophisticated curatorial roles.

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Those new roles will be highly strategic Procurement responsibilities, involving advancing deep learning, reducing the business process, and adding a more effective ethics layer to contracting suppliers.

When Noah was building his Ark on an open plain, his neighbours laughed at him. Months later, they were begging him for a seat on his boat. The future is coming. 1764 was the wrong year to be investing in manual weaving machines. 1861 in single-shot rifles. 1903 in steamboats. 1985 in electric typewriters. 2019 in ATM machines. 2025 in Procurement certifications.

You see my point, or you may not. The Ides of March have come, and they are not going anywhere.

William Gibson said, “the future is already here”. It’s just not packaged for corporate yet. AI is going to replace people who are currently employed to do sourcing activities. You can, of course, debate this. History proves otherwise. It's ok to feel nostalgic. But don't be sad and certainly don't be like the person who once said only businesses will buy computers. Be prepared. It's going to happen in your career lifetime.